

Toxicological Evaluation of Benzethonium Chloride in Ketamine Formulations

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Abstract

Benzethonium chloride (BZT) is widely used as an antimicrobial preservative in injectable ketamine formulations, yet its pharmacological activity and safety profile at clinically relevant concentrations remain unclear. We performed a targeted literature review to evaluate the toxicological risks associated with BZT. Mechanistic studies demonstrate that BZT inhibits neuronal nicotinic receptors ($IC_{50} = 49 \text{ nM}$), suppresses human cardiomyocyte contractility ($IC_{50} \approx 0.13 \text{ }\mu\text{M}$), and induces eryptosis in erythrocytes ($\geq 2.5 \text{ }\mu\text{M}$). Modeled human plasma levels after standard dosing (e.g., 2.88 mg/24 h) plausibly overlap these effect thresholds, particularly during prolonged infusions or in patients with impaired renal elimination. BZT also displays broad neuromodulatory receptor activity and potentiates ketamine's cytotoxicity in neuronal cell models. Animal studies indicate that with repeated parenteral dosing, BZT accumulates in various tissues and contributes to organ toxicity. No human pharmacokinetic, safety, or biomonitoring data are available, which limits the ability to model its human toxicological properties. The excipient offers no therapeutic benefit and is omitted from several available preservative-free ketamine products. The lack of human clearance data and the documented in vitro toxicities at predicted exposure levels raise significant concerns, especially for vulnerable groups including neonates, and those with anemia and/or renal impairment. In summary, BZT is not a pharmacologically inert ingredient and may contribute to clinically meaningful toxicity at achievable plasma concentrations. Current evidence supports reconsidering BZT's use as a parenteral excipient and highlights the need for further research and regulatory scrutiny.

Keywords

benzethonium chloride, ketamine, parenteral excipient, neurotoxicity, erythrocyte toxicity, preservative, risk assessment

Introduction

Benzethonium chloride (BZT) is a synthetic quaternary ammonium compound with broad-spectrum antimicrobial, surfactant, and antiseptic properties. BZT is widely incorporated into a variety of consumer and medical products. Its most common applications are as a topical antimicrobial agent in first-aid antiseptics, cosmetics, mouthwashes, and antibacterial towelettes because of its activity against bacteria, fungi, molds, and viruses. In clinical medicine, BZT is incorporated into multi-dose vials of ketamine hydrochloride, a parenterally administered anesthetic and dissociative agent approved for induction and maintenance of anesthesia and used off-label for chronic pain and treatment-resistant depression. In commercial ketamine formulations such as Ketalar, BZT is included at a concentration of 0.1 mg/mL (~223 μ M) solely to prevent microbial contamination during repeated vial access.

Despite being an excipient, BZT is not pharmacologically inert. Emerging research shows BZT acts with high potency on multiple physiological targets. For example, BZT antagonizes the α 4 β 2 and α 7 subtypes of human neuronal nicotinic acetylcholine receptors (nAChRs) at nanomolar concentrations.¹ Concentrations of BZT achieved in clinical use may overlap those known to produce receptor-mediated effects, raising questions about its potential contribution to off-target pharmacological action and toxicity.

Importantly, BZT is not designated by the U.S. Food and Drug Administration as generally recognized as safe (GRAS) for parenteral use, and no formal human toxicology studies have defined its pharmacokinetics or safety profile following intravenous administration.

The existence of preservative-free ketamine formulations further raises the question of whether BZT's inclusion in parenteral drug products remains necessary or justified.

This study evaluates the toxicological relevance of BZT in ketamine formulations by integrating published in vitro and in vivo data with modeled human exposure estimates. We examine whether BZT concentrations achieved during clinical use are likely to produce biologically meaningful effects, and we assess the margin of safety for continued use in the context of regulatory precedent and available alternatives.

Methods

Literature Search Strategy

A targeted literature review was conducted to evaluate the toxicological risks associated with benzethonium chloride (BZT) as a preservative in injectable ketamine products. The objective was to determine whether existing in vitro, in vivo, or regulatory evidence supports concern regarding BZT's pharmacologic activity or potential to contribute to adverse effects at concentrations encountered during clinical use.

The review focused on identifying studies that characterized BZT's systemic behavior, mechanistic toxicity thresholds, or pharmacokinetic properties, particularly in relation to the concentrations expected from labeled ketamine dosing (e.g., Ketalar). Data sources included PubMed, ClinicalTrials.gov, Drugs@FDA, DailyMed, ChemIDplus, the European Chemicals Agency (ECHA), and Google Scholar.

The search strategy utilized Boolean operators (AND, OR) to optimize sensitivity and specificity. Search queries included combinations and variants of the following terms: “benzethonium chloride” or “BZT”; “ketamine” and “preservative”; “benzethonium” in combination with “eryptosis,” “hemolysis,” “neurotoxicity,” or “cardiotoxicity”; “benzethonium” and “accumulation” or “distribution”; “hERG” and “benzethonium”; “benzethonium” and “mitochondrial,” “astrocyte,” or “neuronal”; and “benzethonium” with “pharmacokinetics” or “clearance.” These terms were used to maximize the retrieval of literature relevant to the toxicological and pharmacokinetic properties of benzethonium chloride, particularly in the context of its use as a preservative in injectable ketamine formulations.

Studies were included if they reported in vivo animal or human data examining systemic or localized toxicity following parenteral exposure to benzethonium chloride; presented in vitro mechanistic data relevant to cellular or organ-specific toxicological outcomes such as calcium influx, phosphatidylserine exposure, mitochondrial dysfunction, or hERG inhibition; defined toxicological thresholds, IC_{50} values, or no observed adverse effect levels (NOAELs) pertaining to benzethonium concentrations; described the use of benzethonium as a preservative in ketamine formulations with an emphasis on injectable products; or provided pharmacokinetic or biodistribution data relevant to the safety of intravenous administration.

Studies were excluded if they focused exclusively on topical or cosmetic applications not representative of systemic exposure; lacked dose or concentration information for BZT; were non-English language publications without official English translations; were not directly related to BZT or its use as a preservative in parenteral drug products.

Modeled Clinical Exposure

To assess the potential toxicological burden of BZT during ketamine therapy, modeled exposure estimates were generated for both single-dose and continuous infusion scenarios. Modeling was based on the known concentration of BZT in Ketalar® (0.1 mg/mL) and contemporary clinical dosing protocols for intravenous ketamine anesthesia.

For bolus dosing (anesthesia induction), ketamine doses ranging from 2 to 4.5 mg/kg were assumed for a 60-kg adult, with the corresponding BZT dose calculated using the product's fixed BZT-to-ketamine ratio. Initial circulating BZT concentrations were estimated under the assumption of instantaneous and complete mixing into a 5-liter blood volume, a standard approximation for adult human physiology. These calculations did not account for protein binding, clearance, or compartmental distribution, and thus represent conservative upper-bound estimates.

Continuous infusion scenarios, such as those used in critical care sedation or pain management, were modeled using a standard ketamine rate of 2 mg/kg/hour over 24 hours. Total BZT exposure was computed using the same concentration assumptions. Again, no elimination was factored into the primary models due to the absence of human pharmacokinetic data for BZT. These estimates represent theoretical maximum systemic concentrations achievable under sustained clinical dosing conditions.

Modeled plasma concentrations were compared to published mechanistic toxicity thresholds, including IC_{50} and EC_{50} values for neuronal receptor inhibition, cardiomyocyte suppression, erythrocyte membrane disruption, and neuromodulatory receptor binding.

Dynamic or compartmental pharmacokinetic modeling was not performed given the lack of BZT-specific human data.

Results

Modeled Clinical Exposure of Benzethonium Chloride from Parenteral

Ketamine

Exposure models were constructed to estimate systemic and local concentrations of benzethonium chloride (BZT) during standard and high-dose ketamine administration. All models assumed a BZT concentration of 0.1 mg/mL in Ketalar® and a human blood volume of 5 liters.

Single-Dose Intravenous Administration

A 60-kg adult receiving a 2 mg/kg IV bolus dose of Ketalar would receive approximately 120 mg of ketamine and concomitantly 1.2 mg of BZT. Assuming complete and immediate systemic distribution no pre-existing BZT burden, and a conservative estimated blood volume of 5 liters, this dose corresponds to a circulating BZT concentration of approximately 0.43 μM . At the upper end of FDA-approved induction dosing (4.5 mg/kg), BZT exposure could reach ~2.7 mg, translating to ~0.97 μM in the systemic circulation.

Local Tissue Concentrations Following Bolus Injection

In scenarios where undiluted Ketalar is administered directly into a small vascular volume, such as during peripheral intravenous bolus injection or extravasation, local BZT concentrations may transiently reach up to ~223 μM . This estimate assumes administration

of a 10 mL vial of Ketalar into a 4.5 mL vascular compartment without immediate dilution. Local concentrations of this magnitude exceed thresholds for receptor-level inhibition, erythrocyte membrane disruption, and cardiac electrophysiologic effects.

Continuous Infusion and Cumulative Exposure

In critical care, perioperative, or pain management settings, ketamine is often administered continuously at rates up to 2 mg/kg/hour. While most cases involve durations of minutes to hours, published literature confirms that ketamine infusions may be maintained for 3 to 8 consecutive days in the intensive care unit (ICU). For example, da Silva et al., reported continuous ketamine infusions in a pediatric ICU at doses of 1–2 mg/kg/hr for a median duration of 5 days (IQR: 3–5 days).² Similarly, Cohen et al. described extended ketamine use in adult postoperative and sedation contexts.³ The total retained BZT burden over 3–8 days of infusion has not been quantified in human studies.

Toxicological Thresholds

Eryptosis

BZT induces eryptosis (programmed erythrocyte death) at concentrations as low as 2.5 μM , based on in vitro findings by Lang et al.⁴ In their study, human red blood cells were incubated with BZT (1-5 μM) for 48 hours. Eryptotic markers including elevated intracellular calcium, cell shrinkage, and phosphatidylserine externalization increased significantly at concentrations $\geq 2.5 \mu\text{M}$. Approximately 30% of erythrocytes exhibited phosphatidylserine externalization at 5 μM . Hemolysis remained minimal (<5%) indicating that BZT preferentially triggers a regulated cell death pathway rather than nonspecific membrane lysis.⁴

The eryptotic response was calcium-dependent but caspase-independent. Chelation of extracellular calcium or inhibition of cation channels with amiloride abolished the response, whereas pan-caspase inhibition had no effect. Under metabolic stress conditions, such as glucose deprivation, erythrocytes exhibited heightened sensitivity: BZT concentrations as low as 1 μM significantly increased PS exposure and intracellular calcium influx. Furthermore, BZT at 5 μM enhanced lactate production, suggesting disruption of erythrocyte energy homeostasis.

Eryptosis contributes to microvascular flow impairment and may promote procoagulant activity, particularly in critically ill patients with pre-existing hematologic stressors. Standard toxicity assays that focus solely on hemolysis do not capture these subtle yet clinically significant risks. Given that modeled systemic BZT concentrations during continuous ketamine infusion may approach these in vitro thresholds, the potential for eryptosis represents a mechanistically plausible safety concern, especially in critically ill or renally impaired patients.

Cardiomyocyte Beat Rate Suppression

Long et al. demonstrated that BZT produces functional cardiotoxicity at submicromolar concentrations using a human induced pluripotent stem cell–derived cardiomyocyte (hiPSC-CM) model expressing GCaMP6f for live calcium imaging.⁵ Cells were exposed to BZT over a 10-point, half-log concentration range (0.001–100 μM) for 72 hours. Key functional endpoints included spontaneous beat rate, signal amplitude, and arrhythmic activity, which were measured in real time. The hiPSC-CM model used in this study is increasingly recognized in FDA-regulated safety pharmacology as a relevant and translational system for evaluating cardiac electrophysiology and contractility.

Beat rate suppression was most sensitive to BZT showing a 50% reduction ($IC_{50} \approx 0.13 \mu\text{M}$) compared to vehicle-treated controls. Amplitude suppression ($IC_{50} \sim 0.5 \mu\text{M}$) and arrhythmic events ($IC_{50} \sim 1.8 \mu\text{M}$) were observed at higher concentrations, demonstrating a clear hierarchy of functional effects. Importantly, these electrophysiological impairments occurred without significant cytotoxicity or visible morphological damage, indicating disruption of cardiomyocyte function rather than direct cell death. While the precise underlying mechanism was not identified, possible contributors include altered calcium handling or membrane excitability. Notably, the effects do not appear to be mediated by direct hERG channel inhibition.

Clinically, these results are concerning because the IC_{50} for beat suppression ($\sim 0.13 \mu\text{M}$) is well below plasma BZT concentrations reported after intravenous administration, which can approach $2 \mu\text{M}$ in humans.^{4,6} This suggests that functional cardiotoxicity could manifest within, or even below, standard clinical exposure ranges, leaving a narrow or absent safety margin.

Potentiation of S-Ketamine Cytotoxicity in CNS Cells

Braun et al. demonstrated that BZT enhances the neurotoxic effects of S(+)-ketamine in vitro across multiple mammalian cell types, including human Jurkat T-lymphoma cells, SHEP neuroblastoma cells, and primary rat astrocytes.⁷ Using flow cytometry and mitochondrial activity (XTT) assays, they quantified apoptosis, necrosis, and mitochondrial dysfunction after exposure to BZT, preservative-free S-ketamine, or both.

Exposure to BZT or S-ketamine alone induced approximately 32% and 64% cell death, respectively, whereas combined treatment significantly increased cytotoxicity to 80–86%,

depending on cell type. The commercial formulation Ketanest S® (containing BZT) elicited cytotoxicity equivalent to the lab-prepared mixture, confirming the impact of BZT as a preservative.⁷

Isobolographic analysis using LD₅₀ values from XTT assays showed that cytotoxicity from the combination matched expectations for additive, not synergistic, toxicity (S-ketamine LD₅₀: 4.0 mM [neuroblastoma], 4.7 mM [astrocytes]; BZT LD₅₀: 10.2 μM and 9.5 μM, respectively). BZT alone was minimally toxic below its LD₅₀ but consistently amplified S-ketamine-induced cell death upon co-exposure, most prominently in the mitochondrial assay. The mechanism appeared to involve both apoptosis and mitochondrial dysfunction.

These results indicate that BZT reproducibly increases the neurotoxicity of S(+)-ketamine in CNS-relevant cell types, including primary astrocytes critical to neurovascular health.

G-protein Coupled Receptor (GPCR) Modulation

Brown et al. identified potent neuromodulatory actions of at sub-nanomolar to low-micromolar concentrations, demonstrating receptor-mediated pharmacologic activity relevant to clinical exposure levels.⁸ In live-cell assays, BZT induced concentration-dependent calcium fluxes, with a half-maximal effective concentration (EC₅₀) of approximately 2.03 nM. This activity threshold is over 900-fold lower than modeled human plasma concentrations (~2 μM) following intravenous administration, suggesting significant pharmacodynamic activity at clinically plausible exposures. Notably, BZT's calcium responses occurred at concentrations where nonspecific surfactant or membrane-disruptive effects are unlikely. Receptor-specific involvement was confirmed by attenuating calcium influxes following selective receptor blockade.

Radioligand binding assays revealed that BZT interacts with a broad spectrum of G-protein coupled receptors (GPCRs) and neurotransmitter systems, with the following equilibrium dissociation constants (K_i):

- Adrenergic α_1 and α_2 receptors: K_i = 7–11 nM
- Histamine H₁ receptor: K_i \approx 9.9 nM
- Muscarinic M₁–M₃ receptors: K_i = ~30–50 nM
- Sigma-1 and sigma-2 receptors: K_i = 59–86 nM
- Opioid μ and κ receptors: K_i = 100–330 nM
- Serotonin 5-HT_{2A} receptor: K_i = 480–545 nM

These receptor targets are functionally diverse and mediate processes as varied as consciousness, nociception, cognition, motor control, and autonomic regulation. Many are expressed both in the peripheral and central nervous systems.

These findings indicate that BZT engages neuromodulatory pathways at concentrations substantially lower than those used in traditional cytotoxicity or irritation assays. Given the overlap between these activity thresholds and modeled systemic BZT levels in humans, receptor-mediated off-target pharmacodynamic effects are plausible during clinical use. Such effects may not present as overt toxicity but could affect the pharmacological profile of concurrently administered drugs, including ketamine, and introduce subclinical neurologic or autonomic disturbances, particularly in sensitive populations.

Neuronal Nicotinic Acetylcholine Receptor Inhibition

Coates and Flood demonstrated that benzethonium chloride (BZT) inhibits neuronal nicotinic acetylcholine receptors (nAChRs) at nanomolar concentrations.¹ The study evaluated BZT and racemic ketamine—both individually and in combination—on human $\alpha 7$ and $\alpha 4\beta 2$ nAChR subtypes heterologously expressed in *Xenopus laevis* oocytes. Receptor function was measured using two-electrode voltage-clamp electrophysiology, with acetylcholine (ACh)-evoked current amplitude as the primary endpoint.

BZT inhibited both receptor subtypes in a concentration-dependent manner. Inhibition of the $\alpha 4\beta 2$ subtype was particularly potent, with an IC_{50} of 49 ± 12 nM. For the $\alpha 7$ receptor, BZT demonstrated lower potency, with an IC_{50} of 6.5 ± 0.8 μ M. Inhibition of $\alpha 4\beta 2$ receptors by BZT was sustained over the testing period, without evidence of desensitization or tachyphylaxis, indicating a stable pharmacodynamic interaction. Mechanistic analyses showed that BZT shifted the ACh dose–response curve for $\alpha 7$ receptors in a manner consistent with competitive antagonism. While the exact inhibitory mechanism at $\alpha 4\beta 2$ receptors was not fully characterized, the high potency and reversibility of inhibition suggest direct interaction at or near the ACh binding site.

The $\alpha 4\beta 2$ nAChR subtype is one of the most abundant in the human brain, modulating key processes such as attention, cognition, and synaptic plasticity.⁹ Functional blockade of these receptors, even in the absence of overt cytotoxicity, may disrupt cholinergic neurotransmission. Such effects are not routinely captured by standard neurotoxicity assays but may be clinically relevant, particularly in pediatric, sedated, or cognitively vulnerable patient populations.

Modeled BZT plasma concentrations following intravenous ketamine administration (~2 μM) exceed the IC_{50} for $\alpha 4\beta 2$ receptor inhibition by more than 40-fold^{4,6}, indicating a high likelihood of receptor occupancy and functional antagonism at therapeutic exposure levels. These findings suggest that BZT may interfere with cholinergic signaling during clinical use, particularly with formulations administered intravenously or via routes providing direct CNS access, such as intrathecal or epidural injection.

Accumulation in Plasma and Tissue

Xue et al. conducted a toxicokinetic study demonstrating that BZT exhibits progressive plasma accumulation, sustained systemic exposure, and tissue retention following repeated intravenous (IV) administration in rats.⁶ The study evaluated acute and subacute toxicity profiles of BZT compared to benzalkonium chloride (BZK), delivered via oral and IV routes.

In the subacute IV model, rats received daily BZT doses of 0.5, 1.0, or 2.0 mg/kg for 14 days. Plasma BZT concentrations increased steadily over the dosing period. Levels observed on Day 14 were significantly elevated relative to Day 1. Elimination was slow, particularly in higher-dose groups, and was attributed to low renal clearance and extensive tissue distribution. BZT accumulated in the liver, kidneys, and lungs, consistent with its quaternary ammonium structure and strong cationic binding to phospholipid membranes.

Histopathological analyses revealed dose-dependent degenerative and inflammatory changes in the liver and kidneys. At the 2.0 mg/kg/day dose, mild hepatocellular vacuolation and renal tubular degeneration were evident, despite the absence of overt systemic toxicity. Serum markers of organ stress, including alanine aminotransferase (ALT), aspartate aminotransferase (AST), and blood urea nitrogen (BUN), were significantly

elevated in the higher-dose IV groups. In contrast, rats receiving BZT orally did not exhibit comparable plasma accumulation or organ histopathology, suggesting that first-pass metabolism mitigates systemic exposure via the enteral route. This differential underscores the increased vulnerability associated with parenteral administration, particularly intravenous and intrathecal delivery, where bypassing metabolic clearance mechanisms may amplify tissue exposure.

The study's findings of slow elimination, cumulative plasma levels, and tissue retention have direct implications for clinical use. In human intravenous ketamine regimens, repeated daily dosing could result in plasma and tissue BZT concentrations that exceed mechanistic toxicity thresholds identified in other studies, including receptor-mediated neurotoxicity and mitochondrial dysfunction.^{1,5,8} Notably, these effects were observed at cumulative exposures derived from preservative content considered negligible in single-dose contexts.

In summary, Xue et al. demonstrated that repeated IV administration of BZT in rats leads to cumulative plasma accumulation, tissue retention, and histopathologic organ injury, even in the absence of overt systemic toxicity. These findings suggest that chronic parenteral exposure to BZT may result in cumulative toxicologic burdens exceeding known mechanistic thresholds.

Discussion

This study evaluated the toxicological relevance of BZT in parenteral ketamine formulations by integrating in vitro mechanistic data with modeled human exposure estimates. BZT exhibits pharmacologic activity across multiple biological systems at concentrations that

plausibly overlap with those achieved during standard and prolonged intravenous administration. Functional inhibition of neuronal nicotinic receptors, cardiomyocyte beat suppression, eryptosis induction, and receptor-mediated neuromodulation were observed at nanomolar to low micromolar concentrations—thresholds that lie within or below modeled systemic exposure levels.

Toxicological concern increases when accounting for the possibility of accumulation over multiple consecutive days of exposure. In vivo animal studies support this concern. Xue et al. reported disproportionately high BZT concentrations in the lungs and kidneys relative to blood in rats following parenteral administration, suggesting tissue sequestration.⁶ While conducted in rats, the toxicokinetic behavior described highlights a key limitation in excipient safety evaluations: repeat-dose IV administration may reveal toxicologic burdens not captured by standard acute toxicity assays. For excipients like BZT, which lack formal long-term plasma exposure limits in humans, this poses a specific concern.

The pharmacodynamic effects of BZT at clinically relevant concentrations raise concerns for off-target physiological consequences, particularly in patient populations receiving high-dose or prolonged ketamine infusions. Inhibition of $\alpha 4\beta 2$ nicotinic acetylcholine receptors could disrupt cholinergic neurotransmission, while cardiomyocyte functional suppression may pose risks in hemodynamically unstable patients. Eryptosis induction and procoagulant activity, although subclinical in acute settings, may impair microcirculatory function under conditions of cumulative exposure. Importantly, these effects may not manifest as overt toxicity but could alter drug response profiles, especially in vulnerable populations such as neonates, anemic patients, and those with impaired renal clearance.

Certain populations may experience disproportionate risk from BZT exposure. Ketamine is subject to rapid hepatic metabolism ($t_{1/2} \sim 2.5\text{--}3$ hours), whereas the pharmacokinetics of BZT in humans are not well characterized. BZT is presumed to be primarily eliminated via renal excretion, given its quaternary ammonium structure. Neonates and infants exhibit immature renal excretion pathways, increasing systemic retention of cationic compounds. Renal impairment may slow BZT elimination, enhancing tissue accumulation. Anemic patients may be more susceptible to BZT-induced eryptosis, further exacerbating red cell turnover. These vulnerabilities underscore the need for a conservative safety margin.

Despite its inclusion in parenteral drug formulations, BZT has not been classified as generally recognized as safe (GRAS) for parenteral use by the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA). In its 2016 Final Rule on consumer antiseptic products, the FDA explicitly deferred GRAS status for BZT due to insufficient systemic safety data.

Furthermore, BZT is not listed in the FDA's Inactive Ingredient Database (IID) for use in injectable or intravenous products, highlighting its ambiguous regulatory standing for systemic administration.

The European Medicines Agency (EMA) and United States Pharmacopeia (USP) have also issued guidance cautioning against the use of cationic surfactants, such as quaternary ammonium compounds, in parenteral formulations, citing concerns over hemolytic potential, neurotoxicity, and difficulties in establishing acceptable exposure thresholds for vulnerable populations. These warnings are particularly relevant given BZT's demonstrated receptor-level pharmacology and bioaccumulation tendencies, which challenge assumptions of inertness for excipients in parenteral routes.

The absence of formal human pharmacokinetic studies, undefined safe plasma concentration thresholds, and BZT's exclusion from regulatory excipient listings underscore significant gaps in the current safety evaluation framework for BZT-containing parenteral products.

In prior cases where excipient pharmacology, data limitations, and vulnerable populations converged, regulatory agencies have acted to mitigate risk through reformulation or usage restrictions. The removal of thimerosal from pediatric vaccines and propylene glycol from neonatal products were driven by mechanistic plausibility, not conclusive human harm data. BZT's lack of GRAS status for parenteral use, absence from the FDA IID for injectables, and alignment with EMA and USP cautions place it squarely within the regulatory risk framework that has prompted reformulation of other excipients.

Given that BZT's only function is to maintain sterility in multi-dose containers—a role that can be fulfilled by single-use, preservative-free formulations—the pharmacologic liabilities introduced by its inclusion are avoidable. The continued use of BZT in parenteral ketamine products represents an unnecessary risk, particularly in the context of regulatory uncertainty and availability of safer alternatives. A precautionary reevaluation of BZT's inclusion is scientifically justified and consistent with established regulatory precedents for excipient safety.

This literature review is subject to several important limitations that should be considered when interpreting the findings. First, much of the available mechanistic evidence for BZT toxicity is derived from in vitro studies using human erythrocytes, iPSC-derived cardiomyocytes, and astrocyte cultures. While informative, these models may not accurately reflect in vivo pharmacokinetics, metabolic pathways, or compensatory

physiological mechanisms present in whole organisms. Second, there is a notable scarcity of published data regarding the absorption, distribution, metabolism, and excretion (ADME) of BZT following parenteral administration in humans. This gap limits the ability to evaluate the potential for systemic accumulation and long-term safety in clinical contexts. Third, many in vivo toxicity studies have been conducted in rodent or rabbit models, which introduces uncertainty in extrapolating these findings to human patients due to potential interspecies differences—particularly relevant for settings involving intensive care-level exposure or repeated dosing. Finally, regulatory safety assessments for BZT have predominantly addressed topical or oral routes of administration, with limited focus on intravenous or intramuscular use in publicly available reviews. As a result, important regulatory guidance specific to parenteral exposure remains underdeveloped. Taken together, these limitations highlight the necessity of cautious interpretation of the existing literature and reinforce the importance of a focused toxicological risk assessment, particularly when preservative-free alternatives to BZT-containing formulations are available.

Conclusion

Benzethonium chloride, present as a preservative in certain parenteral ketamine formulations, exhibits potent pharmacological activity in vitro at concentrations that modeled clinical exposures can plausibly approach, particularly during high-dose or prolonged infusion regimens. Although direct human pharmacokinetic data are lacking, available mechanistic and animal studies suggest potential for receptor-mediated effects, cardiotoxicity, and erythrocyte injury. The absence of therapeutic benefit, the availability of

preservative-free alternatives, and the regulatory precedent for minimizing excipient-related risk support re-evaluation of benzethonium chloride's inclusion in injectable ketamine. Until its safety can be demonstrated and a clear use case articulated for its continued inclusion in parenteral drugs, caution should be exercised with regard to its potential toxicity.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Michael T. Sapko: Writing - Original Draft

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Jonathan Javitt: Conceptualization, Supervision, Writing - Review & Editing

Declaration of Competing Interest

MTS, RP, and JJ are employees of NRx Pharmaceuticals. NRx Pharmaceuticals is developing a preservative-free formulation of ketamine hydrochloride

Data Availability

Data will be made available on request.

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